

Digital Topographic Mapping of the Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology at Benson Idahosa University, Benin City, Edo State

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Abstract

This research focuses on the development of a digital topographic information system for the Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology at Benson Idahosa University (BIU), located in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. It aims to produce a comprehensive digital topographic map and an associated database, using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to enhance area planning and land information management. The methodology includes reconnaissance, data acquisition through primary and secondary sources, and advanced data processing techniques to create detailed maps and models. The results include a comprehensive topographic map showing the perimeter, topography, spot heights and infrastructure within the study area. These maps support diverse applications, from academic research to practical land management, promoting sustainable agricultural practices and effective resource utilization. The research underscores the significant technological advantages of integrating GIS into land management, providing valuable insights for both educational and operational purposes within the faculty.

Keywords: Digital Topographic Information System, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), Benson Idahosa University, Digital Terrain Model (DTM), Spatial Data Analysis

1. Introduction

Topographic maps are critical tools in various fields such as environmental management, urban planning, agriculture, and geology. They provide detailed information about the Earth's surface, including its contours, elevations, and physical features, which are essential for understanding terrain characteristics and planning land use effectively (Chorowicz, 2005). In the context of agricultural education and research, digital topographic maps are indispensable for teaching, planning, and conducting field experiments (García et al., 2012).

The Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology at Benson Idahosa University (BIU) in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria, is dedicated to providing high-quality education and research in agricultural sciences. Accurate and detailed topographic information is crucial for the faculty to enhance its teaching and research capabilities. This necessity underlines the importance of developing a digital topographic map for the faculty.

Topographic mapping has evolved significantly over the past few decades, transitioning from traditional manual methods to advanced digital techniques. Modern topographic maps are created using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS) technologies, which offer high precision and efficiency (Bolstad, 2016). GIS integrates spatial and attribute data to create, manage, analyze, and visualize geographical information, while remote sensing involves acquiring information about the Earth's surface using satellite or aerial imagery (Jensen, 2007).

The application of GIS and RS in topographic mapping provides numerous benefits, including the ability to update maps regularly, integrate various data sources, and perform complex spatial analyses (Goodchild, 2007). These technologies have been widely adopted in agricultural research for purposes such as soil mapping, crop monitoring, and environmental assessment (Corwin & Plant, 2005). By leveraging GIS and RS, educational institutions can develop digital topographic maps that serve as valuable resources for both academic and practical applications (Mulla, 2013).

In Nigeria, the adoption of GIS and RS technologies has been gradually increasing, driven by the need for accurate spatial data for development planning and resource management (Oyinloye & Kufoniya, 2011). However, many academic institutions still lack access to up-to-date topographic maps that reflect the current state of their environments. This gap highlights the need for initiatives to develop digital topographic maps for universities and other educational institutions (Ezeomodo & Igbokwe, 2013).

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The creation of a digital topographic map for the Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology at BIU involves several steps, including data collection, processing, and analysis. Primary data can be collected using Global Positioning System (GPS) devices, while secondary data may be obtained from existing maps, satellite imagery, and other spatial databases (El-Rabbany, 2006). The integration of these data sources in a GIS platform enables the production of a comprehensive and accurate topographic map (Li et al., 2005).

In addition to providing a valuable educational tool, the digital topographic map of BIU's Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology will support various research activities. For instance, it can be used to study the spatial distribution of soil types, analyze watershed characteristics, and plan agricultural experiments (Berry, 1993). Furthermore, the map will facilitate better land use planning and management within the faculty, contributing to more efficient and sustainable agricultural practices (Meyer, 1994).

2. Study Area

The study area for this project is the Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology at Benson Idahosa University (BIU), located in Okha Village within the Ikpoba-Okha Local Government Area of Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. This region serves as a crucial hub for agricultural education and research, making it an ideal setting for the development of a digital topographic map.

Geographically, the site is situated between latitudes 4°30'00" N and 6°30'00" N, and longitudes 5°15'00" E and 6°30'00" E. This location places the faculty in a region characterized by a tropical climate with distinct wet and dry seasons, which significantly influence agricultural practices and research activities. The wet season typically extends from April to October, while the dry season spans from November to March, affecting both the natural vegetation and the soil moisture content in the area (Adejuwon, 2006).

Benin City, the capital of Edo State, is known for its rich cultural heritage and historical significance. It lies within the rainforest zone of Nigeria, which is characterized by dense vegetation, diverse flora and fauna, and fertile soils that are highly suitable for various agricultural activities (Udo, 1978). The region's topography features a mix of flat plains and gently undulating terrain, interspersed with rivers and streams that contribute to the area's agricultural productivity (Odemerho, 1984).

The Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology at BIU is strategically located to leverage these geographical and climatic advantages. The faculty's location within a university environment provides access to academic resources, research facilities, and a community of scholars and students dedicated to advancing agricultural science and technology. The development of a digital topographic map will support the faculty's mission by providing accurate spatial data for planning, teaching, and research purposes.

The study area also includes several agricultural plots, experimental farms, and research stations that are integral to the faculty's educational and research activities. These facilities are used for teaching practical agricultural skills, conducting field experiments, and demonstrating sustainable farming practices. Accurate topographic information is essential for managing these resources effectively, ensuring that land use is optimized for both educational and research outcomes (FAO, 1995).

In addition to its educational and research functions, the study area is part of a broader community that relies on agriculture for livelihoods and food security. The digital topographic map will not only benefit the faculty but also the surrounding community by providing valuable information for sustainable land management and agricultural planning (Ekong, 2003).

3. Methodology

The methodology for this project is comprehensive, encompassing several critical steps designed to ensure the accurate and effective production of a digital topographic map for the Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology at Benson Idahosa University. The process involves the use of both primary and secondary data sources, as well as a combination of software and hardware tools. The methodological approach can be broadly

divided into four main stages: reconnaissance, data acquisition, computation/processing, and map/plan production.

1. Reconnaissance

The initial step in the methodology involves reconnaissance, which is essential for understanding the study area's terrain, accessibility, and logistical requirements. This stage includes:

- a) **Site Visits:** Conducting preliminary visits to the study area to identify key features, assess the terrain, and plan for data collection activities.
- b) **Stakeholder Engagement:** Meeting with faculty members, researchers, and local authorities to gather contextual information and understand specific mapping needs.
- c) **Preliminary Data Review:** Analyzing existing maps, satellite images, and previous studies related to the study area to gather baseline information and identify data gaps (Kraus, 2007).

2. Data Acquisition

Data acquisition involves collecting both primary and secondary data necessary for creating the digital topographic map. This stage includes:

- a) **Primary Data Collection:** Utilizing GPS devices and total stations to capture precise ground control points (GCPs) and elevation data. Field surveys are conducted to gather detailed information about the terrain features, including elevations, slopes, and natural landmarks (El-Rabbany, 2006).
- b) **Secondary Data Collection:** Acquiring satellite imagery and aerial photographs from reliable sources such as the United States Geological Survey (USGS) and other geospatial data repositories. This includes high-resolution images from Landsat 8, Sentinel-2, and MODIS satellites, which provide valuable topographic and land cover information (Jensen, 2007).

3. Computation/Processing

The computation and processing stage involves transforming raw data into usable information through a series of analytical and computational steps. This stage includes:

- a) **Data Preprocessing:** Correcting satellite imagery for atmospheric distortions and geometric errors using advanced image processing algorithms. This ensures the accuracy and reliability of the spatial data (Richards, 2013).
- b) **Data Integration:** Integrating primary and secondary data within a Geographic Information System (GIS) platform. This involves georeferencing, digitizing, and layering various data sets to create a comprehensive spatial database (Bolstad, 2016).
- c) **Digital Elevation Model (DEM) Creation:** Generating a Digital Elevation Model from the collected elevation data to represent the study area's topography accurately. DEMs are essential for visualizing terrain features and conducting further spatial analyses (Li et al., 2005).

4. Map/Plan Production

The final stage involves the production of the digital topographic map, ensuring it meets the required standards and serves its intended purposes. This stage includes:

- a) **Cartographic Design:** Designing the map layout, including the selection of appropriate scales, symbols, and colors to enhance readability and interpretability. The map's design follows established cartographic principles to ensure clarity and accuracy (Slocum et al., 2009).
- b) **Map Compilation:** Compiling the processed data and integrating various map elements, such as contour lines, elevation points, and geographic features, to create the final digital topographic map.
- c) **Validation and Quality Control:** Validating the map's accuracy by cross-referencing it with field observations and existing maps. Quality control measures are implemented to ensure the map's precision and reliability (Longley et al., 2011).

- d) **Distribution and Utilization:** Making the final digital topographic map available for use by faculty members, researchers, and students. The map can be distributed in both digital and printed formats, ensuring broad accessibility and utility.

4. Results

As a result of the comprehensive analyses conducted during this project, several customized maps of the study area were generated. These maps include detailed plans that illustrate various aspects of the terrain and geographic features of the Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology at Benson Idahosa University. The following maps were produced:

1. Perimeter Survey Map:

This map outlines the boundaries of the study area, providing a clear demarcation of the faculty's perimeter. It serves as a foundational reference for all subsequent mapping activities and ensures accurate spatial delineation of the study site (Kraus, 2007).

2. Topographical Survey Map:

This map displays the natural and man-made features of the terrain, including elevations, slopes, water bodies, and infrastructure. It offers a comprehensive view of the landscape, essential for planning and management purposes (Jensen, 2007).

3. Spot Heights Map:

The spot heights map indicates specific elevation points across the study area. These points provide precise elevation data at key locations, which are critical for understanding the topographic variation within the faculty grounds (Li et al., 2005).

4. Digital Terrain Model (DTM):

The DTM represents the study area's terrain surface in a digital format. It provides a three-dimensional visualization of the landscape, showing elevations and depressions with high accuracy. The DTM is a crucial tool for terrain analysis and landform characterization (Bolstad, 2016).

5. Digital Terrain Model with Grid Contour Overlay:

This enhanced DTM includes a grid contour overlay, which adds contour lines to the digital terrain representation. The contour lines illustrate the elevation changes and gradients across the terrain, making it easier to interpret the topographic features and plan for land use accordingly (Richards, 2013).

6. Digital Terrain Model with Grid Vector Overlay:

In this version of the DTM, a grid vector overlay is added to provide a vector-based representation of the terrain features. The grid vectors highlight the direction and magnitude of slopes, assisting in detailed topographic analysis and spatial planning (Longley et al., 2011).

These customized maps are vital for various applications within the Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology. They support educational activities by providing students and researchers with accurate and detailed topographic information. The maps also aid in the planning and execution of agricultural experiments, ensuring that terrain characteristics are considered in research design and implementation (FAO, 1995).

Furthermore, these maps facilitate effective land use planning and resource management within the faculty. They provide a valuable resource for identifying suitable areas for specific agricultural practices, assessing potential environmental impacts, and implementing sustainable land management strategies (Ekong, 2003).

Overall, the generation of these customized maps represents a significant advancement in the faculty's ability to leverage geospatial data for educational and research purposes. The detailed topographic information provided by

these maps will contribute to improved agricultural practices, better resource management, and enhanced educational outcomes, see figures 4.1 and 4.2.

Figure 4.1: Query showing the Composite map and digital topographic outlook of the study area.

Figure 4.2: Query showing the natural shape of the study area.

5. Conclusion

The development of a digital topographic information system for the study area represents a critical advancement in the application of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) for land management. This system leverages modern geospatial technologies to enhance area planning and land information management, offering substantial technological benefits. By focusing on the Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology site at Benson Idaho State University (BIU), this initiative aims to produce a comprehensive digital topographic map and an associated database, which will facilitate a wide range of analyses and the generation of various thematic maps.

Creating a digital topographic information system integrates advanced GIS capabilities, allowing for more precise and efficient land management. This system provides detailed spatial data that supports decision-making processes in multiple domains, including agriculture, environmental management, infrastructure development, and urban planning. By using high-resolution satellite imagery, GPS data, and other geospatial technologies, the system can produce accurate and up-to-date topographic information, which is essential for effective land use planning.

The core output of this project is the digital topographic map of the Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology site at BIU. This map, coupled with its underlying database, serves as a robust tool for various analyses and applications. The digital map provides detailed representations of the terrain, including contour lines, elevation points, and significant geographical features. The associated database stores comprehensive attribute data related to these features, enabling complex spatial queries and analyses.

The digital topographic information system offers numerous benefits to the Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology at BIU. It enhances the faculty's capacity to conduct spatial analyses, model environmental processes, and plan land use effectively. The system supports educational activities by providing students and researchers with access to high-quality spatial data, fostering a deeper understanding of geospatial concepts and applications.

Additionally, the system facilitates sustainable land management by providing accurate information for decision-making, helping to optimize land use and minimize environmental impacts. It also supports the development of agricultural practices that are both productive and environmentally friendly, contributing to the overall goal of sustainable development in the region.

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